

ROLE OF SRIMAD BHAGABAT GITA TO CONTROL STRESS AND PROMOTE POSITIVE MENTAL HEALTH OF TEACHING PROFESSIONALS

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Abstract:

Human life should worship truth, wellness and beauty otherwise known as Satyam, Shivam and Sundaram in Indian context of knowledge. It is the teachers, who make us realize this powerful essence of life to fight against stress and anxiety in different situations of life. It should be the prime concern of the society to make the teachers free of stress and anxiety to get their better service for the universal wellbeing in the present and future of the nation. We should focus on revitalizing the practice of Srimad Bhagabat Gita to fight against stress and anxiety in different context of life. So, this article tries to explore all those powerful principles of Srimad Bhagabat Gita which teaches us how to control and remove stress and anxiety from our peaceful, blissful and valuable life. This article tries to analyze different principles of Sankhyayoga, Karmayoga, Gyanayoga, Bhaktiyoga whose practice would gift us a peaceful, blissful and a prosperous life. So, let's identify different causes of stress and try to remove them by practicing all those applicable and valuable principles of Srimad Bhagabat Gita.

Key words: Sankhyayoga, Karmayoga, Gyanayoga, Bhaktiyoga, Stress, Anxiety, Peace.

Introduction:

An ideal teacher enlightens the lives of many individuals at the cost of his or her time, labour and commitment. This commitment has made teaching profession noble and appreciable. When it lacks appreciation, recognition, commitment or self-esteem it makes the life full of stress. Stress and anxiety are less natural and more manmade, which should be controlled or removed in appropriate socio spiritual environment. This spiritual environment can easily be created by practicing the principles of Srimad Bhagabat Gita in our day-to-day activities. This article tries to realize the essence of Srimad Bhagabat Gita in controlling or removing stress from everyone's life including the teachers.

Objectives of the study:

- To realize the contribution of teachers to the nation
- To study various causes of stress and anxieties of the teachers.
- To realize the role of Srimad Bhagabat Gita in removing stress from our life.
- To analyze different specific principles of Srimad Bhagabat Gita from Sankhyayoga, Karmayoga, Gyanayoga, Bhaktiyoga promoting positive mental health.
- To cite different examples removing and controlling stress by some eminent saints of India.

Brief introduction of Srimad Bhagabat Gita:

Srimad Bhagabat Gita, which is one of the sacred scriptures of India is considered as a book of spiritual guidance and counselling to remove stress, anxieties, instability and hypertension from human minds. Though devotee Arjun and Lord Sri Krishna have built up a client counsellor relationship it possesses an universal relevance of resolving psychological disputes and make people internally calm and positive. While Sakha Arjun represents all the counselees or clients struggling to get relief of a variety stress and anxiety, Lord Sri Krishna represent the community of spiritual Guru and forecited counsellors trying to save them from these disastrous conditions. That's why Maharshi Vyahassadev tried to explain the nature of Srimad Bhagabat Gita in the following verse in its Mangalacharan (Introductory Verses for universal wellbeing)

"Gita sugita kartavya kim anyaih shastra vistaraih, ya svayam padmanabhasya mukha-padmad vinihsrita"

It means all the spoken directions issued by Lord Sri Krishna or Padmanava should be brought into practice which supports to rectify our attitudinal weaknesses leading to a state of stress and anxiety. Srimad Bhagabat Gita discusses the essence of life from different spiritual philosophical and psychological view points and shows the right direction to the common people to overcome their stress and anxiety forever.

Causes of stress in professional workplaces:

- Heavy workload: Teaching is a responsible and stressful profession. Where is responsibility there is stress. Teaching is not only the work of teaching professionals. Sometimes they are forced to be engaged in educational marketing. They try to motivate the children and their parents to take admission in their institution. Many educational institutions provide residential facilities to cater to the emerging needs of the students where the teachers pay their attention towards hostel management and play the role of the hostel superintendent. Sometimes our teachers are obediently assigned with different non-teaching public welfare activities. They conduct the public election at the grass root level. They are engaged in census work and other social surveys conducted by different govt. departments. They take part in the relief and rescue operation at the time of natural calamities for pandemic situations. All these workloads create stress and affect their mental health at any age of life.
- Pressure to maintain high academic performance: Now a days Education is not limited within a single classroom. The scope of Education has crossed the four boundaries of the educational institutions. The academic performance of the students is taken as one parameter of the teacher's performance. We find huge competitions among the educational institutions running under the same board or educational jurisdiction. This competitive spirit has direct impact on the life of the teachers which force them to utilize their educational potentialities and environmental resources to the highest productive level neglecting their personal and private life.
- Problem behaviour management: many children exhibit problem behaviour due to their personal reasons and environmental circumstances. As the student come from different cultural background, disintegration among different culture creates childish disputes which create stress in the minds of the teachers. Communication problem, adjustment problem, inaccessible barriers are some of the other causes that the children bring to the notice of their teachers causing stress and emotional disturbances.
- Parental pressure and interference: Some parents try to impose extra pressure on the teachers to excel the academic performance of their children. It causes stress of the teachers. Sometimes the parent demand extra care and priority for their wards which force the

teachers to act accordingly, giving of their sense of impartiality and nature of honesty which put them in to stress.

- Political interference in school administration: Usually the teachers are come under different political pressure in the process of community mobilization and school level recruitments. Political interference creates unnecessary disputes for the school and the teachers which cause stress and anxiety at large.
- Problem of Adjustment: Sometimes the teachers feel it difficult to adjust with their senior colleagues and the members of the school management committee. Sometimes they are forced to support the malpractice during examination for the shake of the name and fame of the educational institution. This is another factor of maladjustment between the practice and principle of and honest academician.
- Rivalry and competitions: Sometimes the teachers encounter rivalry and competitions in their working places. Competition and rivalry create stress for extra labour to achieve success in this rivalry. This competitive spirit develop anxiety and affect the mental health of the teachers.
- Lack of coordination between the personal and professional life: A teacher is first an individual citizen and then a teaching professional. He or she has his or her personal life attached to the spouse, children, family members, relatives and friends living in the society. They all demand his or her presence, moral support, company, financial support and managerial abilities which is unavoidable in everyone's life. The professional busy schedules force the teachers to neglect his own people, which affect his personal and private relationship. Sometimes the salary does not meet the needs and demands of the families of the concerned teachers for which they try to engage them in private tuitions both in the morning and evenings which makes such life restless and full of anxiety.
- Impacts of social media: The teacher's involvement in social media force them to respond to different stimulations occurred in the digital world. This involvement in the social media spoils the times and distracts the teachers from their usual studies. Many age inappropriate and profession inappropriate visuals helps in growing worldly temptations and mental anxieties in the absence of spiritual consciousness in the life. Sometimes the influence of social media friends and partners spoil the stability and peace of mind, which creates additional stress among the teachers.
- These are some of the exemplary causes of stress and anxiety, which should be removed from the lives of the teachers to maintain the sanctity of this noble profession.

Impact of positive mental health on academic workplaces:

The more an individual regains mental balance and inner strength the better he/she performs in an academic workplace. It is the teachers who not only give classroom instructions but also take care of the positive mental health of their students. If the teachers possess positive mental health, they give an usual smile on their loving lips which removes the fear and increases the quality of inquisitiveness among the fellow learners. While the learners are exposed to positive attitude in a learning environment, they exhibit their creativities and innovative qualities which open the doors of all-round development in a congenial learning atmosphere. Positive mental health largely depends on **self-awareness, emotional regulation, and clarity of thought** as foundations of psycho social well-being. Srimad Bhagabat Gita tries to conceptualise the precious ideas relating to *Karma Yoga* (selfless action), *Bhakti Yoga* (devotion), and *Jnana Yoga* (knowledge) and so on. It guides individuals to perform duties without attachment to outcomes, which ensures reducing

stress, fear, and disappointment in the day-to-day life. The practice of **equanimity (samatva)** teaches acceptance of success and failure equally with a calm mind.

Moreover, the Srimad Bhagabat Gita highlights different ways of ideal spiritual practices like **meditation, maintaining discipline of the mind, and perceiving control over desires** as essential tools for managing stress, achieving inner peace and contentment. The practice of Srimad Bhagabat Gita supports to seek detachment from excessive expectations cultivating resilience against multi various challenges of life. Srimad Bhagavad Gita serves as a practical psychological framework for both learners and academicians that promotes mental stability, self-confidence, and harmony in daily life.

Various stress removing strategies prescribed in Srimad Bhagabat Gita:

Be Sthitapragyan and Control Stress, A message of Sankhya Yoga:

Once swami Dayananda Saraswati was coming back to his ashram after taking bath in the river Ganga. An anti- social man started him scolding without any reason. Swami Dayananda did not react to that person and calmly got on to the steps to catch his way. Another passer by saw this and asked Swamiji why he did not protest the man or punish him in spite of his sound health and physical strength. Swamiji smiled and answered when anyone wants to give us something and we don't receive it; it remains with him. So, when I did not receive these evil words, it remained with him and did not touch me. This is an ideal example of being Stitapragyan in the views of Srimad Bhagabat Gita. Lord Sri Krishna speak

“Dukheshwa Nudwignamanaah Sukheshu Vigataspilah; Veetaraagabhayakrodha Stitadheer munir uchyate.” (2/56). When we are free from the effect of anger, sorrows worry or extremely pleasure we are knowledgeable and self-controlled. This state of mind can easily make us stitapragyan, which means steady and wise. We should try to remain calm and quite within grief or sorrows to remove stress from our mind. We should try to control our anger and develop social tolerance and patience to win over stress and anxiety. We should not even become overwhelmed in pleasure which may cause stress and lead to heart attack, a cause of death and others anxiety. This is not only true in the life of a devotee like Arjun or a saint like swami Dayananda Saraswati rather it is equally true in the lives of all of us who are devoted to the noble profession of teaching.

“Yoga-sthah kuru karmani sangam tyaktva dhananjaya siddhy-asiddhyoh samo bhutva samatvam yoga uchyate”. 2. 48

Yoga means samatwa, oneness, stability of mental and spiritual state of mind. The profession of teaching can be considered as both yoga and karma. As it spreads moral values and economic principles of worldly professions. While we try to attain universal wellbeing, it is Karma. While we talk about the divine power it is a part of yoga. So, if the teachers surrender them before a spiritual Guru, they can better build the moral characters of their students. The capacity of transmission of the divine power can be acquired from the supreme soul and the superior saints to influence the subordinate souls to perform both yoga and karma in a stress-free environment. This transmission of divine power helps in performing a karma (teaching and learning) with full dedication and concentration. While performing yoga or karma we need to give up all those worldly attachments causing stress and instability of mind. We should perceive an equal attitude for both success and failure. It means the teacher needs to pay equal attention towards every individual with a hope of achieving better results but it depends upon the qualities of those students who are admitted to perceive their education under the educational control of the teachers concerned. We can take the examples of traditional Indian Gurukulas where Lord Ram and Krishna pursued their education under the educational control of various Arya Risis. Guru Basistha and Biswamitra were the

teachers of Lord Sri Ram and Guru Sandipani was the teacher of Lord Sri Krishna. Both Lord Sri ram and Sri Krishna had their life full of struggle but could control their stress due to the effects of this yogic karma. Whenever we get stressed, we should try to neutralise its effect on the entire educational environment.

Spirit of karma overcomes stress, says Sankhy Yoga

Sometimes the teachers are worried about the performance of their students and the result of their institutions. Sometimes they compete with other individuals and institutions which causes stress but, the amount of knowledge one is worthy to perceive is pre decided. The educational performance of the learner not only depends upon the style of teaching rather on the inherent qualities, level of intelligent and interest of the learner. So, the teacher should try to realise the relationship between action and results from the following verse of Bhagabat Gita

“Karmanye Vadhikaraste, Ma phaleshou kada chana. Ma karma phala hetur bhurmatey sangostva akarmani”2.47

It means we have the write to initiate an action or karma. Neither its completion nor its outcome is under our control. So, we should concentrate on the nature of work not on the amount of results. Our worries about the result causes stress and its removal removes the stress and helps us maintain our peace of mind. Let’s feel the power of karma from the following story of Dr. Suresh Chandra Devsharma. Dr. Devsharma was a disciple of Sri Sri Thakur Anukul Chandra. He could not get an opportunity of seeking his formal primary school education in his childhood but while Thakur Anukul Chandra owned him as his disciple, he asked him to sit in the matriculation examination at the age of 36. To everyone’s astonishment, Dr. Devsharma not only became a matriculate rather continued his higher studies to get multiple master degree but never worried about his age and future occurrences. In other words, we can say Higher education is not only perceived from the occupational points of views rather it helps us realise the true pleasure of searching for knowledge to get peace and bliss in our life.

Be a Yogi and Control Stress, A message of Dyana Yoga:

As we know stress is a negative force generated from different negative sources of life. So, where there is any kind of negativity, there is stress. While the teacher gets angry with his students, he/she earns stress. While an administrative officer brings allegation false/true it creates stress. While we face financial crises in our life and feel it difficult to fulfil the needs of our beneficiary students or family members, we are put inti stress. While one does not get one’s increment/promotion in time it brings stress. So, all these situational difficulties inspire us to develop tolerance to control or remove all these negative effects from our life by performing different types of Yogas based on our interest and the instructions given by our spiritual gurus. As light removes darkness, knowledge dispels ignorance. We the teachers should realize the power of knowledge and utilize it against all those negative consequence of life. That’s why Lord Sri Krishna advises in this way

**Tapasvibhyodhiko yogi jnanibhyopi matodhikah
karmibhyascadhiko yogi tasmadyogi bhavarjuna 6.46**

It means a yogi is one who performs yoga sit in meditation and have an attachment with the supreme soul. As yoga inspires for self-realization and creates a superior state of mind it removes stress, will of comparison and the spirit of worldly competition, rather possesses a peaceful and blissful state of mind which makes the yogi a superior personality. In this way a yogi is superior to ascetic persons, wise men, action performers. As the teachers perform Gyana Yoga or attachment to

knowledge, they can attain this spiritual power to supersede others having worldly desires. They can easily remove stress and control over their own emotions which destroys one's peace of mind. So, let's attain self-realization through yoga and meditation to acquire positive energy and remove stress from our environment. It was swami Vivekananda who used to sit in meditation for hours to concentrate upon the divine power that connects the souls to super souls. He used to remain silence for a whole day which increased his memory power for which he could grasp the essence of a book within a little span of time.

Knowledge is the power to remove stress, says Gyan, Karma, Sanyasa Yoga:

**Na hi jnanena sadrisam pavitranih vidyate
tatsvayam yogasamsiddhah kalenatmani vindati 4.38**

Knowledge is acquired through yoga. Knowledge is the most sacred thing in this world. True and pure knowledge removes stress and develop sanctity in the heart of the knowledgeable persons. Nothing can be compared to the knowledge in this material world. The span of this life is so short that we can't acquired all shorts of knowledge. So, where time is limited and the scope of knowledge is vast like an ocean we should not lay emphasis on that materialistic aspect of life which creates stress within us. The huge scope of knowledge is felt when we try to analyze multivarious trends of epistemology and metaphysics. When we talk about these two areas of knowledge, we come across the following areas of information about the universe along with the essence of life. Cosmology talks about cosmos or the nature of the universe, which is entirely exhibited by lord Sri Krishna in the Biswarupa Darshan yoga. Ontology talks about real existence of life and regarding this existence Lord Sri Kishna states that

**Aham atma gudakesha sarva bhutashaya-sthitah
aham adish cha madhyam cha bhutanam anta eva cha**

Cosmogony talks about the origine of the universe and the universe is believed to be created by the almighty. So, realization of self is realization of God and realization of God is the realization of universe. So, every teacher should have a dipper connection with the source of all resources. So that stress can't exist at any point of time during sadhana.

Once Gandhiji was in a class where the school inspector came on a visit. The school inspector gave a dictation to check the skill of writing of the children. While writing this dictation Gandhiji misspelt one word which worried his teacher. His teacher asked him to correct his incorrect word copying it from his friend's notebook. Gandhiji did not do it. While the school inspector left the class, the teacher asked him why he could not understand his hint to have a good impression of the visitor. Gandhiji replied that he needed no appreciation by such unfair means and wanted to follow the path of truth. This small story of Gandhiji's life has its relevance in these days. If the teacher tried to get satisfied with what they knew and how they perform they would win over all sorts of stress and anxiety in their life.

We can find relevant statement of Srimad Bhagabat Gita as follows

**Samah shatrau cha mitre cha tathaa maanaapamaanayoh
Sheetoshnasukhadukheshu samah sangavivarjitah.
Tulyanindaastutirmaanee santushto yena kenachit
Aniketah sthiramatir bhaktimaan me priyo narah. (12. 18-19)**

A devotee (A true lover of knowledge) maintains an equal attitude towards enemies and friends, honour and insult, happiness and sorrow, cold and heat, which would save him/her life and professions. It is the ideal of a true devotee that he/she should accept both praise and criticism equally to overcome stress and anxiety caused by these external disturbing elements. One's peace of mind should not be affected by these external factors having no worth for a devotee.

Importance of positive mental health for productive work culture:

Human mind is capable of exploring a lot to resolve all social issues for the sake of universal wellbeing. Human minds are well trained in an adequate educational environment to contribute a lot to the national development. Only a few individuals become the world leaders and lead the human civilization on the path of truth and development. So, every educational institution should take care of their educational environment to promote positive mental health for productive work culture. Positive mental health can be ensured by establishing positive relationship among the inmates and professionals to share and exchange their ideas, opinions and views with constructive attitude. Spiritual activities like Veda Patha, chanting of Gayatri mantras, Gita Gyana Jagyan, divine discourses of saints and spiritual personalities, mass meditation, mass prayers develop positive energy in the environment which inspires to think better, imagine better and explore better to serve the human community in facing the current challenges and resolving the problems of 21st century.

Control of DIET to control the unstable mind:

As human mind is unstable and restless, it is compared to the speediest vehicle of the world. Science has realised that mind is a psychological state reflecting the influence of multiple biological hormones in the brain. The secretion of these biological hormones is controlled by the micro nutrients gained from different food ingredients. These foods increase or classify Tri- dosa i.e. Bata, Kaffa and Pita in the human body. Our food habits and food patterns influence our mental health using the factors of Bata, Kaffa and Pita generating food. While the energy comes out of different foods influence our mental health and creates three types of attitude known as Satwik, Rajasic and Tamasic as described in the seventeenth chapter of Srimad Bhagabat Gita called "Shradhatraya Bibhaga Yoga". The eighth verse of this chapter

**Ayuh-sattva-balarogya-sukha-priti-vivardhanah
rasyah snigdhaḥ sthira hṛidya aharah sattvika-priyah 17.8**

Satwik Ahars develops wisdom, strength, health, happiness, love and span of life, which includes fruits, juice, cowmilk, sprouts and greens. The ninth verse of this chapter states that

**Katvamlalavanaatyushna teekshna rooksha vidaahinah
Aahaaraah raajasasyeshtaa dukhashokaamayapadaah. 17.9**

Rajasic Aharas are bitter, sour, salty, extremely hot, pungent, dry and spicy food which usually creates gas, extra love for food and contribute to instability stress and anxiety. It creates liver related diseases in our body. All sorts of fast food and junk food and packed food other than non-vegetarian components are considered as rajasic Ahar. The tenth verse of the same chapter states that

**Yaatayaamam gatarasam pooti paryushitam chayat
Uchchishamapi chaamedhyam bhojanam taamasapriyam. 17.10**

Tamasic aharas are those which create negative attitudes like anger, irritation, jealousy, lustfulness and destroys the peace of mind. It includes meat, wine, drugs, alcoholic foods, food of previous

night, spoiled food, fire- burnt food, left over food, food producing odd smell or taste and all other unhygienic food that has adverse effect on mental health and hormonal balance of the body.

Conclusion:

Srimad Bhagabat Gita should not be considered as a religious text rather an epitome of numerous principles of stress-free life. Stress is not a disease rather the mother of so many diseases, which should be driven away translating these scientific and holy principles of Srimad Bhagabat Gita into some peaceful and blissful activities in our day-to-day life. Unless an unstable mind is controlled it destroys all positivity from the human life. The content of Srimad Bhagabat Gita should be inculcated in the existing school and college curriculum to impart moral education among the learners and the teachers as well. It is believed that both the chanting and practice of Srimad Bhagabat Gita purifies our body, mind and soul and create positive energy in the working environment. Its chanting develops concentration and peace of mind among the learners which helps them grow their social tolerance and physical stamina to perform well in their studies and other non-academic performance which ensures their all-round development. Let's explore its positive impact on mind and enhance our adherence to this noble profession.

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